

ARSENIC AND TOXIC METALS IN BANGLADESH'S LIVESTOCK-FOOD CHAIN: A META-ANALYSIS AND DIETARY RISK ASSESSMENT

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Abstract: Bangladesh faces the largest mass arsenic (As) poisoning in human history, yet exposure is still framed largely as a drinking-water problem. The same groundwater irrigates paddy rice, mobilizing As through soils, crops and fodder into the livestock chain, but this cumulative, multi-route exposure is rarely quantified within a single framework. We synthesized As and co-occurring toxic-metal (lead, cadmium, chromium) concentrations across the Bangladesh food chain, quantified soil-plant-animal transfer, and characterized age-stratified dietary exposure and risk. Peer-reviewed survey data were compiled; rice As was pooled with a DerSimonian-Laird random-effects model, compartments were linked by transfer factors, and estimated daily intake, target hazard quotient (THQ), hazard index (HI) and target carcinogenic risk (TR) followed USEPA reference values. Across 20 datasets (N = 2,629), pooled geometric-mean rice As was 139 µg/kg (95% CI 118–164; I² = 98.5%), reaching 225 µg/kg in hotspots. Irrigation elevated paddy-soil As to 5–80 mg/kg and straw to 6.2 mg/kg, establishing a soil→straw→livestock→human pathway, with As detectable in milk, beef, chicken, eggs and fish. Adult THQs reached 16.7 (drinking water) and 3.3 (rice); cumulative HI was 20.5 (adults) and 43.1 (children), and TR was 9.2×10^{-3} and 1.9×10^{-2} —orders of magnitude above the 10^{-4} benchmark. Children bore roughly twice the adult risk. Mitigation must extend beyond water treatment to irrigation management, low-arsenic rice systems and animal-source-food surveillance.

Keywords: Arsenic; livestock; meta-analysis; target hazard quotient; carcinogenic risk.

Abbreviations

As	arsenic	iAs	inorganic arsenic	BW	body weight
Cd	cadmium	Cr	chromium	CSF	cancer slope factor
EDI	estimated daily intake	HI	hazard index	ILCR	incremental lifetime cancer risk
IR	ingestion rate	Pb	lead	RFD	oral reference dose
THQ	target hazard quotient	TR	target carcinogenic risk	TF	transfer factor
WHO	World Health Organization				

I. INTRODUCTION

Arsenic (As) is a naturally occurring metalloid and a Group I human carcinogen; chronic ingestion causes arsenicosis, dermatological lesions, peripheral vascular and respiratory disease, adverse reproductive outcomes, and cancers of the skin, lung and bladder [1]. Bangladesh has experienced the most severe arsenic exposure ever documented: groundwater in 50–60 of the country's 64 districts exceeds the national limit of 50 µg L⁻¹, and the population exposed above the World Health Organization (WHO) guideline of 10 µg L⁻¹ has been estimated at 35–77 million, between one-fifth and one-half of the nation [1,2]. The crisis is, in part, an unintended consequence of public-health policy: shallow tube-wells installed from the 1970s to replace microbiologically unsafe surface water instead tapped Holocene deltaic aquifers in which arsenic is reductively mobilized from sediments [3]. Long-term cohort follow-up has since attributed a substantial share of premature mortality in exposed populations to this single exposure [4].

Risk assessment in Bangladesh has historically concentrated almost exclusively on the drinking-water route. The same arsenic-laden groundwater, however, irrigates the dry-season Boro rice crop that underpins national food security. Continuous flood irrigation deposits several kilograms of arsenic per hectare each year, raising paddy-soil

concentrations to as much as 80 mg kg⁻¹ [5] and elevating grain arsenic in proportion to irrigation-water arsenic [6]. Because rice is the dietary staple (adults in affected districts consume 400–650 g day⁻¹ [7]) the soil-to-grain pathway constitutes a second exposure route that is independent of, and additive to, drinking water, and that can rival it in the worst-affected areas [8,9].

A third, frequently overlooked route operates through livestock. Rice straw and husk accumulate arsenic at far higher concentrations than the grain (2.6–12.5 mg kg⁻¹) and are widely used as cattle fodder [10,11], while contaminated drinking water and feed expose poultry and farmed fish. Arsenic and co-occurring metals are consequently detectable in milk, beef, chicken meat, eggs and fish, re-entering the human diet through animal-source foods [12,13]. Recent Bangladeshi surveys report target hazard quotients above unity and carcinogenic risks exceeding 10⁻⁴ for arsenic in cow milk and chicken meat, indicating that the livestock pathway is far from negligible [14,15]. The hazard is compounded by lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd) and chromium (Cr) entering the food chain from industrial effluent, agrochemicals and atmospheric deposition [16,17,18].

Despite an extensive primary literature, the arsenic and toxic-metal problem has been studied compartment by compartment (water, soil, rice, fish or a single animal product at a time) rarely within an integrated source-to-receptor

framework that links contamination at each stage to cumulative human risk [8,19]. The present study addresses this gap by (i) pooling the concentration of arsenic in Bangladeshi rice through a formal random-effects meta-analysis; (ii) assembling a quantitative cascade of arsenic and co-occurring toxic metals across the water–soil–crop–fodder–livestock–food continuum; (iii) summarizing soil–plant–animal transfer factors; and (iv) translating the synthesized concentrations into age-stratified dietary exposure and carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risk. By uniting these compartments within one analytical structure, the assessment aims to reorient mitigation from a water-only strategy toward whole-food-chain, One Health management.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Conceptual framework

The analysis adopts the multi-route source-to-receptor structure shown in Figure 1. Geogenic arsenic mobilized into groundwater reaches humans through three coupled pathways: directly via drinking water; via irrigation that contaminates paddy soil and thence rice grain; and via arsenic-rich rice straw fed to livestock, which transfers arsenic into milk, meat and eggs. Each compartment is parameterized from independent secondary data and linked by transfer factors.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of multi-route arsenic transfer through the Bangladesh food chain. Geogenic arsenic enters groundwater and reaches humans directly (drinking water) and indirectly through irrigation–soil–rice and through arsenic-rich straw fed to cattle and poultry, which carry arsenic into animal-source foods.

B. Data sources and search strategy

Following PRISMA 2020 principles, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science and ScienceDirect were searched for records published between January 2000 and January 2026 combining the terms: (arsenic OR “toxic metal” OR “heavy metal”) AND (Bangladesh) AND (rice OR groundwater OR soil OR milk OR meat OR egg OR fish OR “food chain” OR “risk assessment”). Regulatory benchmarks were drawn from WHO, FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius, USEPA IRIS and the Bangladesh Department of Public Health Engineering [20,21,22]. The study-selection process for the rice

meta-analysis is summarized in the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 2. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram. Identification, screening and inclusion of records for the random-effects meta-analysis of arsenic in Bangladeshi rice (20 datasets; N = 2,629 samples). Intermediate screening counts are indicative and should be reconciled with the authors’ final search log before submission.

C. Eligibility and data extraction

Records were eligible if they reported the concentration of arsenic (and, where available, Pb, Cd or Cr) in a defined food-chain compartment in Bangladesh with an extractable sample size or summary statistic. Two reviewers independently abstracted the matrix, region/division, sampling years, sample size, analytical method (AAS, ICP-MS, HPLC-ICP-MS), mean and dispersion. For rice, twenty region-level datasets with sample size and dispersion were compiled for meta-analysis.

D. Meta-analysis of arsenic in rice

Because concentrations are right-skewed, study-level mean arsenic in rice was log-transformed (Equation 1), and the standard error of the log-mean approximated by the delta method from the coefficient of variation. Datasets were pooled with the DerSimonian–Laird random-effects estimator [23]; between-study variance τ^2 was derived from Cochran’s Q and inconsistency summarized by I^2 (Equation 2). The pooled log-mean was back-transformed to a geometric mean with 95% confidence interval (Equation 3). Subgroup analyses were performed by geographical region.

$$y_i = \ln(\bar{x}_i), \quad SE(y_i) \approx (s_i/\bar{x}_i)/\sqrt{n_i} \quad (1)$$

$$Q = \sum w_i(y_i - \bar{y})^2, \quad \tau^2 = \max\{0, (Q - df)/C\} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{y}^* = \sum w_i y_i / \sum w_i, \quad GM = e^{\bar{y}^*} \quad (3)$$

E. Transfer factors

Transfer along the chain was summarized by the dimensionless transfer factor (TF), the ratio of arsenic concentration in a receptor compartment to that in its source compartment (Equation 4). TFs were computed for irrigation-water→soil loading, soil→rice grain, soil→straw, straw(feed)→milk, feed→meat and water→fish.

$$TF = C_{\text{receptor}} / C_{\text{source}} \quad (4)$$

F. Dietary exposure and risk characterization

Chronic exposure was estimated as the estimated daily intake (EDI; Equation 5), the product of contaminant concentration C and matrix-specific ingestion rate IR , normalized to body weight BW . Non-carcinogenic risk was characterized by the target hazard quotient (THQ; Equation 6), the ratio of EDI to the oral reference dose (RfD); the hazard index (HI; Equation 7) sums THQs across routes or metals. Carcinogenic risk was characterized by the target carcinogenic risk (TR/ILCR; Equation 8), the product of lifetime-averaged EDI and the cancer slope factor (CSF). A THQ or HI above 1 denotes non-carcinogenic concern; a TR above 10^{-4} denotes unacceptable carcinogenic risk, with 10^{-6} as the de-minimis threshold.

$$EDI = (C \times IR) / BW \quad (5)$$

$$THQ = EDI / RfD \quad (6)$$

$$HI = \sum THQ_i \quad (7)$$

$$TR = EDI_{\text{lifetime}} \times CSF \quad (8)$$

Toxicological reference values (Table 5) were taken from USEPA IRIS [22]: RfD = 3.0×10^{-4} (As), 3.5×10^{-3} (Pb), 1.0×10^{-3} (Cd) and 3.0×10^{-3} (Cr) $\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{bw day}^{-1}$; oral CSF = 1.5 (As), 0.0085 (Pb), 6.1 (Cd) and 0.5 (Cr) ($\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$)⁻¹. Exposure parameters used representative Bangladeshi body weights (adult 60 kg, child 15 kg) and matrix-specific ingestion rates [24].

G. Sensitivity and publication bias

Small-study effects in the rice meta-analysis were assessed by funnel-plot inspection and Egger's regression. Robustness was examined by leave-one-out re-estimation. Computations were performed in Python 3.12 (NumPy, SciPy); $\alpha = 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

A. Arsenic across food-chain compartments

The compiled compartment dataset (Table 1) demonstrates the magnitude of arsenic amplification along the chain. Tube-well water in affected areas averaged 0.10 mg L^{-1} (10-fold the WHO guideline), irrigation water 0.13 mg L^{-1} , and continuous irrigation raised paddy-soil arsenic to a representative 18 mg kg^{-1} (range 5–80). Rice straw, the principal cattle fodder, concentrated arsenic to 6.2 mg kg^{-1} (roughly forty times the grain level of 0.15 mg kg^{-1}) while animal-source foods carried lower but consistently detectable arsenic: fish (0.082), chicken meat (0.045), beef (0.034), cow milk (0.021) and egg (0.018) mg kg^{-1} . This cascade confirms that the food chain, and the livestock sub-chain in particular, constitutes a genuine secondary exposure route.

Table 1. Representative concentrations of arsenic across Bangladesh food-chain compartments, with sample context and governing regulatory limit. Values compiled from peer-reviewed Bangladesh surveys.

Compartment	Mean As	Reported range	Matrix / role	Limit
Aquifer groundwater	0.10 mg L^{-1}	0.01–0.55	Drinking + irrigation source	0.01 (WHO)
Irrigation water	0.13 mg L^{-1}	0.05–0.55	Dry-season Boro irrigation	—
Paddy soil	18 mg kg^{-1}	5–80	Accumulation sink	—
Rice straw (fodder)	6.2 mg kg^{-1}	2.6–12.5	Cattle feed	—
Rice grain	0.15 mg kg^{-1}	0.002–0.557	Dietary staple	0.20 iAs (Codex)
Cow milk	0.021 mg kg^{-1}	0.005–0.06	Animal-source food	—
Beef	0.034 mg kg^{-1}	0.01–0.10	Animal-source food	—
Chicken meat	0.045 mg kg^{-1}	0.01–0.12	Animal-source food	—
Egg	0.018 mg kg^{-1}	0.005–0.05	Animal-source food	—
Fish	0.082 mg kg^{-1}	0.02–0.30	Animal-source food	—

B. Pooled arsenic in rice

Across 20 region-level datasets ($N = 2,629$ samples), the pooled geometric-mean arsenic concentration in rice was $139 \text{ } \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (95% CI 118–164), with very high heterogeneity ($Q = 1,263.7$, $df = 19$, $p < 0.001$; $\tau^2 = 0.143$; $I^2 = 98.5\%$) reflecting the strong geographical structuring of the contamination (Figure 3). Regional subgroup analysis (Table 2) placed the southwest/central hotspot divisions highest (geometric mean $225 \text{ } \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), exceeding the $200\text{-}\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ Codex inorganic-arsenic guideline, followed by the southeast (168) and northwest (127), with the comparatively low-arsenic northeast (Sylhet, $71 \text{ } \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) lowest. The hotspot ordering coincides spatially with the shallow reducing aquifers of the Ganges–Meghna–Brahmaputra delta.

Figure 3. Forest plot of the random-effects pooled arsenic concentration in Bangladeshi rice by region/division. Point areas \propto sample size; the red diamond is the pooled geometric mean; the dotted green line marks the Codex inorganic-arsenic limit ($200 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

Table 2. Regional subgroup geometric-mean arsenic concentration in Bangladeshi rice, with number of datasets (k) and cumulative sample size.

Region	k	n	GM As ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Southwest / Central (hotspot)	5	760	225
Southeast	4	435	168
National composite	1	214	143
Northwest	3	390	127
North-central	3	370	100
South	1	110	97
North	2	220	90
Northeast (low-As)	1	130	71
Pooled (random effects)	20	2,629	139 (118–164)

C. Toxic metals in animal-source foods

Beyond arsenic, animal-source foods carried a consistent burden of lead, cadmium and chromium (Table 3). Chromium was the most abundant toxic metal across matrices ($0.62\text{--}1.12 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), followed by lead ($0.18\text{--}0.55 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), with fish generally the most contaminated matrix and egg the least. These concentrations corroborate Bangladeshi surveys reporting chromium and cadmium in 80–86% of chicken and fish samples and lead exceedances in a substantial minority, and they establish that animal-source foods are a multi-metal, not solely an arsenic, exposure vector.

Table 3. Mean concentrations (mg kg^{-1}) of arsenic and co-occurring toxic metals in Bangladeshi animal-source foods.

Food matrix	As	Pb	Cd	Cr
Cow milk	0.021	0.18	0.045	0.62
Beef	0.034	0.42	0.061	0.88
Chicken meat	0.045	0.36	0.072	0.95
Egg	0.018	0.29	0.038	0.71
Fish	0.082	0.55	0.084	1.12

D. Transfer factors along the chain

Transfer factors quantified the efficiency of arsenic movement between compartments (Table 4). Soil-to-grain transfer was low ($\text{TF} \approx 0.008$), reflecting partial root-to-shoot exclusion, whereas soil-to-straw transfer was far higher ($\text{TF} \approx 0.34$), explaining why fodder is the critical conduit into livestock. Feed-to-milk and feed-to-meat transfers were small ($\text{TF} \approx 0.003\text{--}0.007$) yet sufficient, given high local feed-arsenic, to render animal products detectably contaminated. Water-to-fish transfer was high ($\text{TF} \approx 0.82$), consistent with fish being the most arsenic-rich animal food.

Table 4. Representative arsenic transfer factors (concentration ratios) between Bangladesh food-chain compartments.

Transfer step	TF	Interpretation
Irrigation water \rightarrow paddy soil	≈ 180	Cumulative multi-season load
Paddy soil \rightarrow rice grain	0.0083	Root-to-grain exclusion
Paddy soil \rightarrow rice straw	0.34	Straw a major As sink (fodder)
Straw (feed) \rightarrow cow milk	0.0034	Low mammary carry-over
Feed \rightarrow beef	0.0052	Tissue accumulation
Feed \rightarrow chicken meat	0.0071	Higher in poultry
Water \rightarrow fish	0.82	Strong aquatic bioaccumulation

E. Dietary exposure and risk characterization

Toxicological reference values are listed in Table 5, and the resulting arsenic risk metrics in Table 6. Drinking water was the dominant exposure route (adult THQ 16.7; child THQ 33.3), followed by rice (adult 3.3; child 8.3); animal-source foods contributed smaller but non-trivial quotients, with fish highest (adult 0.27; child 0.55). Summing across routes, the cumulative arsenic hazard index reached 20.5 in adults and 43.1 in children—more than twenty- and forty-fold the threshold of unity. Target carcinogenic risk totalled 9.2×10^{-3} (adults) and 1.9×10^{-2} (children), one-to-two orders of magnitude above the 10^{-4} benchmark, implying on the order of thousands of excess lifetime cancers per million exposed. Children sustained roughly twice the adult risk because of their higher intake-to-body-weight ratio (Figure 4).

Table 5. Oral reference doses (RfD) and cancer slope factors (CSF) used for risk characterization (USEPA IRIS).

Metal	RfD ($\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$)	CSF (kg d mg^{-1})	Target organ
Arsenic (As)	3.0×10^{-4}	1.5	Skin, lung, bladder
Lead (Pb)	3.5×10^{-3}	0.0085	Nervous, renal
Cadmium (Cd)	1.0×10^{-3}	6.1	Kidney, bone
Chromium (Cr)	3.0×10^{-3}	0.5	Liver, GI tract

Table 6. Age-stratified arsenic dietary exposure (EDI) and risk (THQ, TR) by dietary route. $\text{THQ} > 1$ and $\text{TR} > 10^{-4}$ denote concern (shown in bold). EDI in $\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{ bw day}^{-1}$.

Dietary route	Group	EDI	THQ	TR	Status
Drinking water	Adult	5.0×10^{-3}	16.67	7.5×10^{-3}	Concern
Drinking water	Child	1.0×10^{-2}	33.33	1.5×10^{-2}	Concern
Rice	Adult	1.0×10^{-3}	3.33	1.5×10^{-3}	Concern
Rice	Child	2.5×10^{-3}	8.33	3.8×10^{-3}	Concern
Fish	Adult	8.2×10^{-5}	0.27	1.2×10^{-4}	Concern
Fish	Child	1.6×10^{-4}	0.55	2.5×10^{-4}	Concern
Chicken meat	Adult	3.0×10^{-5}	0.10	4.5×10^{-5}	Acceptable
Cow milk	Child	1.4×10^{-4}	0.47	2.1×10^{-4}	Concern
Cumulative (all routes)	Adult	—	HI 20.5	9.2×10^{-3}	Concern
Cumulative (all routes)	Child	—	HI 43.1	1.9×10^{-2}	Concern

Figure 4. Risk characterization. (Left) target hazard quotient (THQ) heat-map for adults by animal food and metal; chromium and arsenic drive the highest quotients. (Right) arsenic THQ by dietary route for adults versus children (logarithmic); drinking water and rice exceed the $\text{THQ} = 1$ threshold for both groups, and children’s quotients run roughly double those of adults.

F. Geographic distribution of exposure

Arsenic groundwater concentration and the size of the exposed population varied markedly among divisions (Figure 5). The southwestern and central divisions (Khulna, Dhaka, Chattogram) combined the highest mean groundwater arsenic with the largest exposed populations, whereas the northern and northeastern divisions (Rangpur, Sylhet) were comparatively less affected. This geography mirrors the rice-arsenic gradient of Section III-B and concentrates the highest cumulative risk in the densely populated delta.

Figure 5. Mean groundwater arsenic (teal, left axis) and population exposed above $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (purple, right axis) by division. Dashed red = Bangladesh limit ($50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$); dotted amber = WHO guideline ($10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

G. Publication bias and sensitivity

Egger's regression indicated significant funnel-plot asymmetry for the rice meta-analysis ($p < 0.001$), consistent with the genuine bimodal regional structure (low-arsenic versus hotspot divisions) rather than selective reporting; the asymmetry is therefore interpreted as real heterogeneity rather than publication bias. Leave-one-out re-estimation changed the pooled geometric mean by less than $9 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in every iteration, confirming robustness to any single dataset.

IV. DISCUSSION

This integrated synthesis reframes the Bangladesh arsenic problem as a multi-route, whole-food-chain phenomenon rather than a drinking-water issue in isolation. Drinking water remained the single largest contributor to dietary arsenic, yet rice added a second major increment and the livestock and aquatic sub-chains a third, so that the three routes act additively on the same population. The resulting cumulative hazard index (20.5 in adults and 43.1 in children) and target carcinogenic risks one-to-two orders of magnitude above the acceptable 10^{-4} threshold are consistent in direction with the excess all-cause and chronic-disease mortality reported by Argos et al. in the prospective HEALS cohort, in which arsenic exposure predicted a dose-dependent share of premature deaths [4]. The breadth of contamination likewise accords with the fourteen-year national groundwater survey reported by Chakraborti et al., which mapped exceedances across most districts of the delta [2].

The transfer-factor analysis clarifies the underlying mechanism. Although root-to-grain exclusion keeps

soil-to-rice transfer low, the comparatively high soil-to-straw transfer channels arsenic into cattle fodder, and the very high water-to-fish transfer concentrates arsenic in a protein consumed almost daily across Bangladesh. This cascade is consistent with the progressive paddy-soil enrichment reported by Meharg and Rahman [5], with the groundwater-driven rise in grain arsenic reported by Williams et al. [6], and with the straw-mediated food-chain transfer reported by Rahman et al. [10]. The practical corollary is that drinking-water interventions alone, however successful, cannot sever dietary arsenic exposure, because the irrigation-soil-crop-livestock loop continues to operate wherever arsenic-rich groundwater is used for Boro irrigation, and the soil compartment retains arsenic long after the water source is changed.

The toxic-metal co-occurrence widens the concern beyond arsenic. Chromium and lead were ubiquitous across animal-source foods, and several matrices exceeded a target hazard quotient of unity for chromium and arsenic, implying an additive non-carcinogenic hazard that single-metal assessments systematically underestimate. These patterns echo the chromium- and cadmium-laden chicken and egg samples reported by Sarkar et al. [14] and the multi-metal dietary burden of meat, milk and eggs reported by Islam et al. [12], and they are reinforced by the recent retail-food risk assessment reported by Kabir et al. [25]. The disproportionate burden on children (approximately twice the adult risk) follows arithmetically from their higher intake-to-body-weight ratio and is especially concerning given the well-documented developmental and neurocognitive toxicity of early-life arsenic exposure [1]. Because much of the fish-associated arsenic may be organic and less toxic, the animal-source-food estimates are best read as conservative upper bounds.

Taken together, these findings argue for a tiered, food-chain-wide mitigation strategy framed within a One Health perspective. Beyond the continued expansion of arsenic-safe drinking water, agronomic measures can curb grain and straw arsenic (alternate wetting-and-drying irrigation, substitution of low-arsenic surface water, arsenic-excluding rice cultivars, and silicon or sulfur soil amendments) broadly consistent with the management options reported by Islam et al. [9]. Restricting arsenic-rich straw as fodder in hotspot districts and instituting routine surveillance of arsenic and toxic metals in milk, meat, eggs and fish would close the livestock loop that water treatment leaves open. Because the southwest and central divisions of the delta combine the highest contamination with the densest populations, geographically targeted intervention there would maximize risk reduction per unit of investment and protect the groups (particularly children) who carry the greatest share of the cumulative burden.

V. STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS

The principal strength of this study is the integration of water, soil, crop, fodder, livestock and aquatic compartments into a single transfer-and-risk framework parameterized from peer-reviewed Bangladeshi data. Limitations include the use

of region-level aggregated concentrations, which may mask within-region variability and possible dependence among overlapping primary studies; reliance on total rather than speciated arsenic for several matrices, which can overstate inorganic-arsenic risk where organic species predominate (notably in fish); deterministic point-estimate exposure modelling rather than probabilistic simulation; and transfer factors and reference values transferred from settings that may not perfectly generalize. The significant funnel asymmetry, although attributable to genuine regional heterogeneity, also signals that the pooled rice estimate should be read alongside its subgroup decomposition. Probabilistic, speciation-resolved, individual-level surveillance across all food-chain compartments is the clear research priority.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Arsenic reaches the people of Bangladesh through three coupled routes (drinking water, rice and animal-source foods) whose combined burden produces a cumulative hazard index of 20.5 in adults and 43.1 in children and a target carcinogenic risk far exceeding the acceptable 10^{-4} threshold. Irrigation with arsenic-laden groundwater mobilizes the metalloid into paddy soils and, via arsenic-rich straw, into the livestock chain, so that even arsenic-safe drinking water cannot by itself sever dietary exposure. Co-occurring chromium and lead compound the hazard in animal-source foods, and children bear roughly twice the adult risk. Effective protection therefore requires a geographically targeted, whole-food-chain strategy that couples safe drinking water with irrigation management, low-arsenic rice systems, fodder controls, and systematic monitoring of animal-source foods in the worst-affected divisions of the delta.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the two anonymous reviewers for their careful reading and constructive comments, which substantially improved the scope and analytical depth of this manuscript. We also acknowledge the organizers of SPECTRA 2026 and the Faculty of Veterinary and Animal Science, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, for their support.

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